

Colorimetric Analysis of Water Quality Monitoring System for Heavy Metal Detection

Gokul M^{*1}, Sabarish K², Rakshan Darwin I³, Seetharaman R⁴

¹Student, Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Student, Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Student, Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu, India.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu, India.

Corresponding author(s):

DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18360736>

Gokul M, Student, Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Saranathan College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email: gokuldhoni75@gmail.com

Citation:

Gokul M, Sabarish K, Rakshan Darwin I, Seetharaman R (2026). Colorimetric Analysis of Water Quality Monitoring System for Heavy Metal Detection. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions, 8(1), 42–58. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18360736>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Accepted: 20 January 2026

Available online: 22 January 2026

Abstract

The contamination of water by heavy metals is a danger to both mankind and nature. The presence of heavy metals, including zinc, copper and nickel, above certain limits can lead to massive biological and ecological destruction. Traditional, laboratory-based methods of detecting heavy metals are accurate but expensive and take too long, so they are not suited for real-time monitoring. This paper describes a low-cost, Internet of Things (IoT) enabled heavy metal detection system that uses a TCS3200 colour sensor in conjunction with selective chemical reagents. The sensors indirectly detect the presence of zinc sulphate ($ZnSO_4$), copper chloride ($CuCl_2$) and nickel sulphate ($NiSO_4$) through the comparison of reagent-induced colour changes (i.e., colourimetric). The sensor data is processed by an ESP32 microcontroller, which communicates with the ThingSpeak Cloud for real-time monitoring and visualisation. The results of experiments show that the proposed system is reliable for the detection of metals